

METHODOLOGY OF MASTERING LISTENING AS A TYPE OF SPEECH AND LEARNING ACTIVITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685910>

ELSEVIER

Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna

Karshi engineering - economics Institute, senior teacher at Foreign Languages
Department
gulbakhormansurova69@gmail.com

Abstract: Today, listening occupies a significant place in the methodology of teaching German. As we know, listening is a process of perceiving and understanding foreign speech by ear. The article is devoted to the process and methodology of mastering listening as a type of speech and learning activity in higher education.

Keywords: German, types of speech activity, listening and speaking skills, exercises, means of communication.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 22-02-2023

Accepted: 22-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

Introduction:

More and more people are required to speak a foreign language as a means of communication. And this, in turn, affects the change and refinement of the goals of teaching German in different types of educational institutions. So, in the current program for higher educational institutions, the main goal of education is formulated as follows: the development of students' abilities to use a foreign language as a communication tool in the dialogue of cultures and civilizations of the modern world. Moreover, the "dialogue of cultures" is understood not only as an acquaintance with the culture of German-speaking countries, but also as acquaintance with the peculiarities of the life and life of the Uzbek, the spiritual heritage of Uzbekistan and its contribution to world culture.

In the first year of study in higher education institutions, the communicative and speech development of students begins. They will have to master the oral form of communication, i.e., learn to understand foreign speech by ear and respond to it accordingly. That is why the author pays great attention to learning to listen, since this type of speech activity forms the basis of communication, mastering oral communication begins with it. This allows the teacher to fully appreciate the benefits of listening in teaching German at the initial stage, as it provides students with rich language material and speech patterns [1,152].

Literature Review:

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, there are several ways of teaching listening: as a means of teaching other types of speech activity and as a learning goal. According to Galskova N.D. [1], listening as a means can be used as:

a way of organizing the educational process; the method of introducing language material orally; means of teaching other types of speech activity; means of control and consolidation of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities. Based on the works of Galskova N.D. and Gez N.D. [2], who believed that the thoughtful organization of the educational process (clarity and consistency of presentation, maximum reliance on language experience, a variety of ways of presentation) allows you to direct students' attention to those points that will help program their future activities with perceived material, the author concludes that it is necessary to present students with a clear setting before listening to the text, depending on which, perception will be either passive or active, contributing to successful memory activity [15, 32]. Listening is a receptive activity, and mastering receptive activities is a prerequisite for the development of productive skills and, first of all, speaking.

ANALYSES AND DISCUSSIONS:

Listening - understanding of the speech perceived by the ear - forms the basis of communication, mastering oral communication begins with it. It consists of the ability to differentiate perceived sounds, integrate them into semantic complexes, keep them in memory while listening, carry out probabilistic forecasting and, based on the communication situation, understand the perceived sound chain. Speaking and listening are two interrelated aspects of oral speech. Listening is not only the reception of a message, but also the preparation in inner speech of a response to what is heard. Thus, listening plays an important role in learning German by students at the initial stage of education. It is both a goal and a powerful learning tool. It makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress, melody. Through listening in the first year, the lexical side of the language and its grammatical structure are mastered. And at the same time, listening makes it easier to master speaking.

In the process of teaching listening in the first year at higher educational establishments, the teacher should draw the attention of students to what is important from the first lessons [2,611]:

- listen carefully,
- concentrate on what the teacher and students say,
- try to correlate this with a specific situation, facial expressions, gestures and other non-verbal means.

Students need to be taught a culture of listening. They should understand from the first lessons that the ability to listen is the key to success in learning German. The first and most necessary condition for the formation of students' understanding of German speech is that the teacher conducts a lesson in German. Hence, great demands are placed on the speech of the teacher. The main ones are:

- Normativity (correctness) of speech,

- Its usualness (that's what a native speaker will say in this situation),
- Selection and repetition of language means,
- Adequacy of students' ability to understand it,
- Emotionality and artistry.

Listening is used as a means of introducing students to new language or speech material: to organize an acquaintance with new material means to show students the meaning, form and use of it. So, when introducing children to new vocabulary, in order to master the form, it is necessary for students to repeatedly perceive it; to understand the meaning, you can use the non-translating method of revealing the meaning, and only if necessary - translation; situations are needed to illustrate the use of a new word. Familiarization begins with the perception of the whole, i.e., the statement - a speech unit correlated with the situation. Thus, it goes from the whole to the particular, from the statement to a single word, and from it to the sound (if it is new). What is required to select situations that reveal the communicative function (what can be conveyed using this word).

- Choose a structure for the presentation of the word in order to give an integrated lexical, pronunciation, grammatical side of the statement.

- Consider whether you need to use your native language.

- Provide comprehension of the meaning of words (without translation) and exercise control, i.e. check with specific tasks how students understood them (zeigen, nehmen, tun), or an adequate reaction (ja, nein oder muttersprachliche Äquivalente).

The choice of a method for disclosing the meaning of a word depends on a number of factors. Among them are linguistic (the nature of the word itself), psychological and pedagogical.

If the word has a specific meaning and it can be demonstrated, for example, **ein Hund, eine Katze, ein Ball, rot, groß, klein** then it is advisable to reveal the meaning of the word using visualization, rather than resorting to translation.

In the case of an abstract meaning of a word like **denken**, it is better to use a translation.

International words like **Arzt, Sport, Fußball, Ingenieur** should be guessed in the appropriate context.

If the word is entered in a non-translational way, then the control understanding should be carried out without resorting to the native language. Only in this case it will be guessed, which is so necessary when listening. The choice of the method of semantization is also influenced by the psychological factor, for example, the general development of the students in the group. The level of training also influences, that is, the possession of general methods of teaching. The

higher the level of learning, the more opportunities for non-translational semantization.

And finally, the pedagogical factor: the size of the group, the time that the teacher has to familiarize students with new vocabulary, the qualifications of the teacher.

The larger the group, the more often the teacher is forced to resort to semantization through translation as the most time-saving method, leaving more time for exercises in using the word. The more qualified the teacher, the greater the arsenal of techniques he owns, the less often he turns to translation when he uses listening as a means of teaching a new word.

For example:

Übungen, die darauf abzielen, die Aufmerksamkeit der Schüler zu entwickeln ("Hören Sie zu und sagen Sie den Namen von Mikes Schwester: Ich habe eine Schwester. Ihr Name ist Ann. Mike hat keine Schwester. Er hat einen Bruder.")

Übungen zur Entwicklung der Vorstellungskraft („Hören Sie zu und sagen Sie in einem Wort weiter: Der Ort, an dem wir Sportspiele spielen").

Listening is used as a learning tool, and it is also the goal of learning. In the first year in higher education, this is listening to a connected text in a sound recording or read by a teacher.

Sequence of working with text:

- removal of difficulties (if there are new words, it is necessary to familiarize students with them)

- preparing for the first listening,

- first audition

- checking understanding, based on the preparation for the first listening,

- installation on the second listening,

- second audition

- checking understanding, based on the second installation

When teaching, students should have a clear understanding of learned vocabulary and flexible use of knowledge of grammar. Pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar are the three main elements that make up the language system and are also the foundation for student improvement. Teachers should properly guide students to memorize words according to pronunciation rules, and complement some cultural background knowledge and common idioms at different levels and angles to expand students' knowledge. On the other hand, listening practice should be combined with acquired grammatical knowledge, and in order to consolidate grammatical knowledge, it is necessary to perform some sentence building exercises or dictation exercises. Dictation exercises can be done in a variety of ways: Dictation materials can use sentences and paragraphs from the text, or they can be

rewritten in parts of the text. Dictation materials should be moderately difficult so as not to dampen the enthusiasm of the students.

CONCLUSION:

Listening is the key to success in learning a foreign language. The teacher should stop the desire to translate messages in a foreign language into their native language, since translation slows down and simply slows down the formation of the ability to understand sounding foreign language speech. It follows from the foregoing that the formation of listening comprehension should proceed in the natural conditions of sounding speech, which is the task of the teacher of the speaker or the speaker on the audio recording to simulate in the classroom. Therefore, in the process of teaching listening, it is necessary focus on developing students' ability to fully represent, reflect and summarize content in accordance with their language knowledge, cultural background knowledge and mother tongue knowledge.

REFERENCES:

1. Buxorova, M. X., Mansurova, G. M., & Eshmurodov, U. K. (2021). FORMATION OF STUDENTS COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (2), 152-154. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44813098>
2. Bukharova, M. K., Mansurova, G. M., & Ishonkulova, N. T. (2019). MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING THE GERMAN LANGUAGE AT UNIVERSITIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (11), 611-613. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42407804>
3. Kaiser F.-J., Kaminski H. *Methodik des Oekonomie-Unterrichts. Grundlagen eines handlungsorientierten Lernkonzeptes mit Beispielen.* –Bad Heilbrunn, 1999, 200-218
4. Mansurova, G. M., Eshonkulova, N. T., & Eshmurodov, U. K. (2021). THE TRAGEDY OF “JULIUS CAESAR”. *Социосфера*, (1), 54-56. http://www.sociosfera.com/files/conference/2021/sociosfera_1-21.pdf#page=55
5. Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna. (2022). Teaching the Interpretation of a Literary Text in German Lessons. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 6, 27-31. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/803>
6. Mansurova, G. M., & Fayzieva, K. A. (2020). GENERAL CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION CATEGORY. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(8), 227-230.

https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=1242523419625242789

7. Mansurova, Gulbahor and Fayzieva, Kamila (2019) "EVALUATION CATEGORY IN FOREIGN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES ACCORDING TO THEIR PRAGMATIC CHARACTERISTICS," Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 1: Iss. 2, Article 41. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/namdu/vol1/iss2/41>

8. Nurmuradova, Shakhnoza Ibragimovna, Peculiarities and Some Issues of Learning Vocabulary (February 1, 2021). TJE - Tematics journal of Education ISSN 2249-9822, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3783104> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3783104>

9. Nurmuradova Shakhnoza Ibragimovna. (2022). Actual Problems of Modern Methods of Teaching the Russian Language. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 4, 147-152. <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/515>

10. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna. (2021). LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTS. Euro-Asia Conferences, 41-44. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/529>

11. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>

12. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna, & Azimova Maftuna Shavkatovna. (2021). USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING English. Euro-Asia Conferences, 14-17. Retrieved from <http://papers.euroasiaconference.com/index.php/eac/article/view/519>

13. Soliyeva, M. A. (2018). Teaching speaking for non-linguistic students. Проблемы

14. Бим И.Л. Методика обучения иностранным языкам как наука и проблемы школьного учебника. - М.: Русский язык, 1977. - 288 с

15. Гальскова, Н.Д. Современная методика обучения иностранным языкам: Пособие для учителя / Н.Д. Гальскова. - М.: АРКТИ, 2004 - 191 с. 8. Гез, Н.И. Роль условий общения при обучении слушанию и говорению. / Н.И. Гез. // Иностранные языки в школе. - 1981 - № 5 - С. 32-40

16. Гез Н.И., Ляховицкий М.В., Мирлобов А.А. и др. «Методика обучения иностранным языкам в средней школе»: учебник. - М.: Высш. шк., 1982.

17. Нурмурадова, Ш. И. (2016). Формирование у студентов интереса к профессии учителя в процессе педагогической практики. Молодой ученый, (9), 1162-1163. <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25964478>

18. Нурмурадова Ш.И. Инновационные педагогические технологии в вузе при подготовке специалистов // Вестник по педагогике и психологии Южной Сибири. 2014. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/innovatsionnye-pedagogicheskie-tehnologii-v-vuze-pri-podgotovke-spetsialistov>